

The Interaction of Transition Metal Derivatives with Macrocyclic Alkadiynes

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Reactions of the macrocyclic alkadiynes 1, 7-cyclododecadiyne, 1, 7-cyclotridecadiyne, 1, 7- and 1, 8-cyclotetradecadiyne, and 1, 8-cycloptadecadiyne with the metal carbonyls $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$, $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$, $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{M}(\text{CO})_2$ ($\text{M}=\text{Co}$ and Rh), $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$, and $[\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NiCO}]_2$ are reviewed. The following types of reactions have been found in these systems: (1) Formation of products retaining the macrocyclic alkadiyne structure; (2) Intramolecular transannular cyclization of the macrocyclic alkadiyne to form tricyclic cyclobutadiene, cyclopentadienyl, or metallacyclopentadiene derivatives; (3) Intermolecular cyclization of two macrocyclic alkadiyne units to form metallacyclopentadiene derivatives.

REACTIONS of transition metal derivatives with alkynes, $\text{RC}\equiv\text{CR}'$ have provided a variety of unusual organometallic compounds.^{1,2} In some cases such reactions lead to simple alkyne-metal complexes as exemplified by the formation of a wide range of (alkyne) Co_2 ($\text{CO})_6$ (I) and (alkyne) Ni_2 (C_5H_5)₂ (II) complexes from alkynes and $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ or $[\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NiCO}]_2$, respectively. In other cases, two or more alkyne units undergo cyclization in the presence of the transition metal system to form cyclobutadiene³ or benzene⁴ metal complexes. In cases where metal carbonyl derivatives are used one or more carbonyl groups can cocyclize with the alkyne units to form metal complexes of cyclic systems such as cyclopentadienones⁷, quinones⁸, or tropones⁹ as exemplified by the iron tricarbonyl complexes III, IV & V, respectively. In other cases metallacyclic systems are formed, parti-

cularly metallacyclopentadienes^{7,10} such as the tricarbonylferrole-iron tricarbonyls VI.

In 1968 when we started our studies on the reactions of metal carbonyls with macrocyclic alkadiynes, very little was known about reactions of alkadiynes with transition metal derivatives. Some reactions between alkadiynes of the type $\text{RC}\equiv\text{C}-\text{C}\equiv\text{CR}'$ and iron carbonyls had been shown¹¹ to give iron tricarbonyl (II) derivatives of cyclopentadienones and tricarbonylferroles retaining one uncomplexed carbon-carbon triple bond from the two present in the original 1, 3-alkadiyne. Considerably more interesting was the identification by X-ray crystallography¹² of the unusual iron monocarbonyl complex VII from the reaction of iron pentacarbonyl with *o*-bis (phenylethynyl) benzene.

We selected for our studies the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII ($m=4, n=4, 5, \text{ and } 6$; $m=5, n=5$ and 6), which could be obtained in relatively good yields by the cyclization of the disodium derivatives of the α, ω -alkadiynes $\text{HC}\equiv\text{C}(\text{CH}_2)_m\text{C}\equiv\text{CH}$ with the α, ω -dibromoalkanes $\text{Br}(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{Br}$ in liquid ammonia^{1,2}. These macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII were of interest since the saturated polymethylene chains linking the two carbon-carbon triple bonds were expected to hold these carbon-carbon triple bonds in fixed geometries which might control the course of their cyclizations with transition metals. Accordingly, we purchased samples of the five macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII ($m=4, n=4, 5, \text{ and } 6$; $m=5, n=5$ and 6) from the Farhan Research Laboratories and studied their reactions with a variety of transition metal carbonyl derivatives. We isolated tractable organometallic products from reactions of these macrocyclic alkadiynes with the metal carbonyls

reactions of $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ and $[\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NiCO}]_2$ with macrocyclic alkadiynes parallel exactly their reactions with simple alkynes.

Reactions of the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII with $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ in a hydrocarbon solvent at room temperature proceed readily over a period of hours to form the red crystalline tetrametallic derivatives (alkadiyne) $[\text{Co}_4(\text{CO})_6]_2$ (IX: $m=4, n=4, 5$ and 6 ; $m=5, n=5$ and 6). Similarly the reactions of the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII with $[\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NiCO}]_2$ in boiling benzene give the dark green crystalline tetrametallic derivatives (alkadiyne) $[\text{Ni}_4(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2]_2$ (X: $m=4, n=4, 5$ and 6 ; $m=5, n=5$ and 6). In the complexes of both types IX and X, both of the carbon-carbon triple bonds of the macrocyclic alkadiyne are complexed with pairs of metal atoms and the macrocyclic ring is retained

$\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$, $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_{12}$, and $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ as well as the cyclopentadienylmetal carbonyls $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{M}(\text{CO})_2$ ($\text{M}=\text{Co}$ and Rh) and $[\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NiCO}]_2$. This paper reviews the highlights of our work in this area. Further details are provided in four preliminary communications^{1,4,15,16,17} and four full papers.^{18,19,20,21}

Complexes Retaining the Macrocyclic Alkadiyne Unit: The Products from $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ and $[\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NiCO}]_2$: The simplest reactions of the macrocyclic alkadiynes are those in which their carbon-carbon triple bonds form transition metal complexes with retention of the macrocyclic ring system. Such complexes are obtained by reactions of the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII with $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ and with $[\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NiCO}]_2$ under relatively mild conditions¹⁹. As indicated above, these two metal carbonyl systems react with simple $\text{RC}\equiv\text{CR}'$ alkynes under mild conditions to form the corresponding $(\text{RC}\equiv\text{CR}')\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_6$ (I) and $(\text{RC}\equiv\text{CR}')\text{Ni}_2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$ (II) complexes, respectively. Thus the

Some attempts were made to prepare bimetallic $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ and $\text{Ni}_2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$ derivatives of the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII in which only one of the two carbon-carbon triple bonds is involved in complex formation with the transition metal system. Such products of the types (alkadiyne) $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_6$ (XI: $m=n=4$) and (alkadiyne) $\text{Ni}_2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$ (XII: $m=n=4$) are obtained from similar reactions of 1,7-cyclododecadiyne (VIII: $m=n=4$) with $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ and $[\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NiCO}]_2$, respectively, in a 1:1 mole ratio. However attempts

to prepare similar (alkadiyne) $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ (XI) and (alkadiyne) $\text{Ni}_2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$ (XII) derivatives from the other macrocyclic alkadiynes gave only non-crystalline products which could not be fully purified.

Intramolecular Transannular Cyclizations of the Macrocyclic Alkadiynes to Tricyclic Cyclobutadiene Derivatives: The Products from $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{M}(\text{CO})_2$ ($\text{M}=\text{Co}$ and Rh) A particularly obvious reaction pathway of the macrocyclic alkadiynes upon treatment with transition metal derivatives is the intramolecular 2+2 cycloaddition of the two carbon-carbon triple bonds to form a tricyclic cyclobutadiene derivative. Such compounds are obtained from the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII and the cyclopentadienylmetal dicarbonyls $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{M}(\text{CO})_2$ ($\text{M}=\text{Co}$ and Rh).^{1,4,18,21}

The reactions of $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{Co}(\text{CO})_2$ with the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII proceed readily in boiling n-octane ($\sim 126^\circ$) to give the yellow to yellow orange tricyclic cyclobutadiene derivatives of the stoichiometry $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{Co}$ (alkadiyne)(XIII: $\text{M}=\text{Co}$, $m=4$, $n=4$, 5, and 6; $m=5$, $n=5$ and 6)^{14,18}. The compounds XIII ($\text{M}=\text{Co}$, $m=4$, $n=5$; $m=n=5$) can also be obtained by displacement of the 1,5-cyclooctadiene ring in $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{Co}(1,5\text{-C}_8\text{H}_{14})$ by the macrocyclic alkadiyne in boiling cyclooctane ($\sim 150^\circ$).

XIII

The following evidence supports the structures XIII ($\text{M}=\text{Co}$) for these complexes of stoichiometry $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{Co}$ (alkadiyne): (1) The absence of any $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ or $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{C})$ frequencies in their infrared spectra as well as a general resemblance in the 1530-800 cm^{-1} regions of their infrared spectra to that of cyclopentadienylcyclobutadienecobalt, $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{CoC}_4\text{H}_4$; (2) The presence of only cyclopentadienyl and saturated CH_2 resonances in their proton n.m.r. spectra; (3) The formation of different but isomeric products from the reactions of $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{Co}(\text{CO})_2$ with the isomeric macrocyclic alkadiynes 1,8-cyclotetradecadiyne (VIII: $m=n=5$) and 1,7-cyclotetradecadiyne (VIII: $m=4$, $n=6$).

The preparation of tricyclic cyclobutadiene cobalt complexes of the structure XIII ($\text{M}=\text{Co}$) from the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII and $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{Co}(\text{CO})_2$ suggested the corresponding reactions of the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII with the rhodium analogue $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$. These reactions were of particular interest,

since at that time cyclobutadiene-rhodium complexes of any type were unknown. In this connection, reactions of $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ with the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII in boiling cyclooctane were found to give 15 to 68% yields of white to pale yellow volatile tricyclic cyclobutadiene derivatives XIII ($\text{M}=\text{Rh}$, $m=4$, $n=4$, 5, and 6; $m=5$, $n=5$ and 6)²¹. Their physical and spectroscopic properties correspond completely to those of the analogous cobalt derivatives XIII ($\text{M}=\text{Co}$) discussed above.

The formation of the tricyclic cyclobutadiene-rhodium derivatives XIII ($\text{M}=\text{Rh}$) in fair to good yields from the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII and $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ shows how the restricted orientations of the two carbon-carbon triple bonds in the macrocyclic rings can modify the interaction of these triple bonds with transition metal systems. Similar reactions of $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ with the simple alkynes $\text{RC}\equiv\text{CR}$ ($\text{R}=\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$ and C_6H_5) in boiling cyclooctane do not give any of the corresponding cyclobutadiene-rhodium derivatives $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{RhC}_4\text{R}_4$ although bimetallic and trimetallic derivatives of other types and not containing cyclobutadiene units have been obtained from these latter reactions.

A frequent reaction pathway of $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{M}(\text{CO})_2$ ($\text{M}=\text{Co}$ and Rh) with simple alkynes $\text{RC}\equiv\text{CR}$ is the formation of the corresponding cyclopentadienone complexes $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{MC}_4\text{R}_4\text{CO}$ (XIV: $\text{M}=\text{Co}$ and Rh , $\text{R}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ and CF_3)^{22,23,34}. However, no evidence for the formation of any similar tricyclic cyclopentadienone complexes was obtained from any of the reactions of $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{M}(\text{CO})_2$ with the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII. Apparently, the relative orientations of the two carbon-carbon triple bonds in the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII are restricted by the polymethylene bridges to prevent the insertion of a carbonyl group before a 2+2 cyclization to form a cyclobutadiene derivative.

XIV

Some of the reactions of $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{M}(\text{CO})_2$ with the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII were found to give interesting products in addition to the tricyclic cyclobutadiene derivatives XIII. The reaction of 1,8-cyclotetradecadiyne with $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{Co}(\text{CO})_2$ in boiling cyclooctane gives not only the tricyclic cyclobutadiene derivative $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{CoC}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}$ (XIII: $\text{M}=\text{Co}$, $m=5$, $n=5$) but also a black trimetallic derivative of stoichiometry $(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8)_3\text{Co}_3(\text{CO})\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}$ with an unknown structure²⁸.

The reactions of $C_8H_8Rh(CO)_2$ with the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII were found to give a wider variety of products besides the tricyclic cyclobutadiene derivatives XIII ($M=Rh$) discussed above²¹. The reaction of 1,7-cyclododecadiyne with $C_8H_8Rh(CO)_2$ besides giving $C_8H_8RhC_{12}H_{16}$ (XIII: $M=Rh$, $m=n=4$) also gives a colorless $C_{24}H_{32}$ dimer of 1,7-cyclododecadiyne. Proton n. m. r., ultraviolet, and Raman spectra indicate that three of the four carbon-carbon triple bonds of the two 1,7-cyclododecadiyne units form a benzenoid ring in this dimer. The reaction of 1,8-cyclotetradecadiyne with $C_8H_8Rh(CO)_2$ gives in low yield an orange bimetallic derivative of approximate stoichiometry $(C_8H_8)_2Rh_2(C_{14}H_{20})_2(CO)_n$ ($n=1$ or 2) with an unknown structure. In addition the reactions of macrocyclic alkadiynes with $C_8H_8Rh(CO)_2$ give erratic yields of purple products of apparent stoichiometry $(C_8H_8)_3Rh_3(C_8H_{12})_3(CO)_2$ which appear to arise from the cyclooctane solvent.

Reactions of Iron Carbonyls with Macrocyclic Alkadiynes: The trichoric analogy²⁸ between C_8H_8Co and $Fe(CO)_3$ groups suggested that reactions of iron carbonyls with the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII might result in 2+2 cycloaddition to give tricyclic cyclobutadiene-iron tricarbonyl derivatives of stoichiometry (alkadiyne) $Fe(CO)_3$ and structure XV. However, the only macrocyclic alkadiyne which was found to react with iron carbonyls to give significant quantities of a tricyclic cyclobutadiene derivative is 1,7-cyclotetradecadiyne (VIII: $m=4$, $n=6$), which gives yellow liquid $C_{14}H_{20}Fe(CO)_3$ (XV: $m=4$, $n=6$) with $Fe(CO)_5$ or $Fe_2(CO)_9$.^{16,20}

Reactions of iron carbonyls with macrocyclic alkadiynes containing at least one pentamethylene bridge result in 2+3 intramolecular transannular cyclizations to give tricyclic cyclopentadienyl rather than cyclobutadiene derivatives. Thus reactions of $Fe_3(CO)_{12}$ or $Fe(CO)_5$ with the macrocyclic alkadiynes containing pentamethylene bridges VIII ($m=5$, $n=4, 5$, and 6) give the dark red crystalline $[(alkadiyne-H)Fe(CO)_2]_2$ derivatives XVI ($m=5$, $n=4, 5$, and 6).^{16,20} These products may be regarded as substitution products of $[C_8H_8Fe(CO)_2]_2$ in which four of the five hydrogens on each cyclopentadienyl ring are replaced by alkyl groups. The yields of the tricyclic cyclopentadienyliron dicarbonyl dimers XVI are the highest in the formation of $[C_{14}H_{18}Fe(CO)_2]_2$ (XVI: $m=5$, $n=5$) from 1,8-cyclotetradecadiyne, which contains two pentamethylene bridges. The tendency for only macrocyclic alkadiynes containing at least one pentamethylene bridge to form tricyclic cyclopentadienyl derivatives of the type XVI may relate to the ease of formation and minimum strain in a six-membered ring fused to the cyclopentadienyl system relative to either a five-membered ring (where the angular strain would be too high) or to seven-membered and larger rings (which would form with more difficulty).

The reactions of the $[(alkadiyne-H)Fe(CO)_2]_2$ derivatives XVI resemble those of the prototype $[C_8H_8Fe(CO)_2]_2$.²⁰ Thus the reductions of the $[(alkadiyne-H)Fe(CO)_2]_2$ derivatives with sodium amalgam in tetrahydrofuran give the sodium salts $Na[Fe(CO)_2(alkadiyne-H)]$ as indicated by reactions of the resulting solutions with triphenyltin chloride to give the triphenyltin derivatives $(C_8H_8)_3SnFe(CO)_2(alkadiyne-H)$ (XVII) and

XV

XVI

XVII

XVIII

XIX

with hexafluorobenzene to give the pentafluorophenyl derivatives $C_6F_5Fe(CO)_2$ (alkadiyne-H) (XVIII). The iron-iron bond in $[C_{14}H_{10}Fe(CO)_2]_2$ (XVI: $m=5$, $n=5$) can also be cleaved with iodine in boiling chloroform to give the corresponding iodide $C_{14}H_{10}Fe(CO)_2I$ (XIX). A characteristic feature of all of these tricyclic cyclopentadienyl derivatives is the presence of a singlet proton n.m.r. resonance at τ 5.5 to 6.0 corresponding to the single proton on each of the cyclopentadienyl rings.

The remaining macrocyclic alkadiyne of which the reactions with iron carbonyls have been studied is 1,7-cyclododecadiyne (VIII: $m=n=4$). Since a pentamethylene bridge is not present in 1,7-cyclododecadiyne, this hydrocarbon does not form a tricyclic cyclopentadienyliron dicarbonyl dimer derivative of the structural type XVI. Furthermore, only a very low yield of the corresponding tricyclic cyclobutadiene derivative XV ($m=n=4$) is formed from the reactions of 1,7-cyclododecadiyne with iron carbonyls. The major product from the reaction between 1,7-cyclododecadiyne and $Fe(CO)_5$ is a tricarbonylferrole-iron tricarbonyl derivative of the stoichiometry $C_{12}H_{10}Fe_2(CO)_6$. X-ray crystallographic studies by Chen and Bau²⁶ on this complex indicate the previously unexpected structure XX. In order to form XX from 1,7-cyclododecadiyne (VIII): $m=n=4$ and iron carbonyls, cleavage of one of the carbon-carbon bonds in the twelve-membered ring is required. Presumably the relative ease of forming six-membered rings from the polymethylene bridges is the driving force behind this novel carbon-carbon bond cleavage.

XX

XXI

XXII

XXIII

XXIV

The formation of products of the types XV, XVI, and XX from reactions of various macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII with iron carbonyls all involve various types of intramolecular cyclizations. The reaction of 1,7-cyclotridecadiyne with $Fe(CO)_5$ also gives a yellow tricarbonylferrole-iron tricarbonyl derivative of stoichiometry $(C_{13}H_{10})_2Fe_2(CO)_6$ which must necessarily involve intermolecular cyclization of the carbon-carbon triple bonds from two 1,7-cyclotridecadiyne units with the $Fe(CO)_5$ unit to form the tricarbonyl-ferrole ring. Structures such as XXI ($m=4$, $n=5$) may be proposed for this complex, but an unambiguous decision between several different positions of the non-equivalent polymethylene bridges must await an X-ray crystallography study.

In an attempt to find a method for preparing the intermolecularly formed tricarbonylferrole-iron tricarbonyl derivatives (XXI) from the other macrocyclic alkadiynes (VIII), their reactions with benzalacetone-iron tricarbonyl, $[C_6H_5CH=CHCOCH_3]Fe(CO)_3$, were investigated. Previous work²⁷ had indicated that this iron carbonyl reagent is a good source of $Fe(CO)_3$ groups under mild conditions. Reactions of all five macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII ($m=4$, $n=4,5$, and 6 ; and $m=5$, $n=5$ and 6) with benzalacetone-iron tricarbonyl were found to give the desired intermolecular dimerization products XXI¹⁷. The success in preparing these tricarbonylferrole-iron tricarbonyl derivatives also led to an investigation of the reactions of benzalacetone-iron tricarbonyl with the simple alkynes $RC\equiv CR$ ($R=CH_3$, C_2H_5 , and C_6H_5). These reactions were found to provide good methods for the preparation of the simple tricarbonylferrole-iron tricarbonyl derivatives $R_4C_4-Fe_2(CO)_6$ (VI: $R=CH_3$, C_2H_5 and C_6H_5). In this way our work on the metal carbonyl chemistry of the macrocyclic alkadiynes suggested a new and useful method for converting simple alkynes into the interesting metalocycles VI.

The success in preparing unusual organoiron¹⁷ carbonyl derivatives from various reactions of iron carbonyls with the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII suggested reactions of iron carbonyls with other macrocyclic compounds containing two unsaturated functionalities separated by polymethylene bridges. In this connection

the macrocyclic diallenes of the types XXII ($n=2$ and 5) were found to undergo transannular cyclization with $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_{12}$ to give the tetramethyleneethane diiron hexacarbonyl derivatives XXIII ($n=2$ and 5).²⁸ The simple unsubstituted tetramethylene:thane diiron hexacarbonyl, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_6$ (XXIV), was shown several years ago²⁹ to arise from the dimerization of allene, $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$, in the presence of $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_{12}$.

Summary

The macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII are of interest in representing systems in which the relative orientations of the two potentially reactive carbon-carbon triple bonds are restricted by the two polymethylene bridges. The reactions of the macrocyclic alkadiynes VIII with metal carbonyls can be classified into the following categories :

(1) Formation of products retaining the macrocyclic alkadiyne structure as exemplified by the complexes (alkadiyne)[$\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_6$]₂ (IX) and (alkadiyne)[$\text{Ni}_2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$]₂ (X).

(2) Intramolecular transannular cyclization of the macrocyclic alkadiyne to form products of any of the following three types :

- (a) Simple intramolecular 2 + 2 cyclization without hydrogen shift or carbon-carbon bond cleavage to form tricyclic cyclobutadiene derivatives such as XIII (M=Co and Rh) or XV.
- (b) Intramolecular transannular 2 + 3 cyclization with hydrogen shift but without carbon-carbon bond cleavage to form the tricyclic cyclopentadienyl derivatives XVI.
- (c) Intramolecular transannular cyclization with carbon-carbon bond cleavage and metal insertion as exemplified by the formation of the metallocycle XX.

(3) Intermolecular oligomerization as exemplified by the formation of the tricarbonylferrole-iron tricarbonyl derivatives XXI.

The macrocyclic diallenes XXII have also been shown to undergo intramolecular transannular cyclization to form the bicyclic tetramethyleneethane derivatives XXIII.

The work summarized in this paper thus shows how macrocyclic and transition metal chemistry can be combined to give a variety of unusual organometallic compounds and reactions. Some of these reactions may suggest new catalytic processes for preparing useful and interesting organic compounds from alkyne and olefin raw materials. Furthermore, extensions of reactions such as those discussed in this paper to larger

macrocyclic systems containing three or more carbon-carbon triple bonds and to other transition metals should also be possible. We have already observed interesting products from some of the macrocyclic alkadiynes and certain platinum metal halides such as the hydrated trichlorides of rhodium and iridium. Further study of this area of chemistry is likely to lead to new results at least as unusual and significant as those described in this paper.

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